

Extractive spectrophotometric determination of ruthenium(III) with 4-(benzylideneimino)-5-methyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol

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Abstract : A simple, highly sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method is proposed for the extraction of micro-gram level concentration of ruthenium(III) with 4-(benzylideneimino)-5-methyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (BIMTT) as an extractant at pH 5.4 in chloroform. The optimum pH range for extraction of complex is 4.5–6.5. The method obeys Beer's law in the range 10 ppm to 50 ppm, a molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of $1.52 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.066 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively at 394 nm. The effect of reagent concentration, pH, equilibration time and various foreign ions has been investigated. The method is applicable to determine ruthenium(III) from synthetic mixture corresponding to Fission alloys.

Keywords : Ruthenium(III), solvent extraction, chloroform, Fission alloy.

Introduction

Ruthenium is a scarce element that is found in about 0.001 ppm of the earth crust. It is present in much larger amount in chondrite, and especially in iron meteorites ($(1-6) \times 10^{-4}\%$). It usually occurs in association with other platinum group metals¹. Liquid-liquid extraction technique has been used for the separation of platinum group metals²⁻⁵. Other extractants reported for ruthenium(III) are di(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid⁶, tributyl phosphate⁷, *N*-octylaniline⁸ and trioctylamine (TOA)⁹.

An important characteristics of Ru^{III} is that it prefer to coordinate most strongly with 'soft' bases containing polarizable atoms such as sulfur, phosphorous and nitrogen according to the empirical Pearson classification¹⁰. Sulphur containing ligands are highly selective for extraction of Ru^{III}, and have been widely used in the extraction of this species¹¹⁻¹⁴. The 4-(benzylideneamino)-5-methyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (BIMTT), a sulphur containing ligand, is highly water repellent and does not form emulsion at the time of extraction. We report here the use of BIMTT (Fig. 1) as an extractant for the separation and determination of ruthenium.

Fig. 1. Structure of 4-(benzylideneimino)-5-methyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol

Results and discussion

Effect of pH on the extraction of ruthenium(III) :

Keeping all the conditions constant, extraction behavior of the ruthenium(III)-BIMTT complex in terms of absorbance was investigated over the pH range 1–10. The absorption spectra of the light yellow complex in chloroform indicate maximum observed at 394 nm (Fig. 2). The absorbance at maximum wavelength remained unchanged between pH 4.5–6.5 (Fig. 3). The nature of the spectral curve remained constant indicating the formation of only one species of ruthenium(III) complex under these conditions. Hence the use of sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer of pH 5.4 gives satisfactory pH control and is recommended for further studies.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of ruthenium(III)-BIMTT complex in chloroform.

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on Ru^{III}-BIMTT complex : Ru^{III} = 10 ppm.

Effect of equilibration time :

Variation of the shaking period from 5 s to 5 min showed that a minimum 1 min equilibration time is adequate for quantitative extraction of ruthenium(III) in chloroform. As a general procedure, 1 min of equilibration time is recommended in order to ensure complete extraction of ruthenium(III) with BIMTT at pH 5.4 (acetate buffer solution). Prolonged shaking up to 5 min has no adverse effect on the efficiency of extraction.

Effect of diluents :

Various organic solvents have been tried as extractants for the metal complex. The extraction behaviors (in terms of absorbance) decrease in the order : chloroform > carbon tetrachloride > xylene > toluene > benzene > isobutyl methyl ketone > ethyl acetate > isoamylalcohol > *n*-butanol > 4-methyl-2-pentanol. In chloroform, the absor-

bance remains unchanged for more than 24 h. Hence, chloroform is chosen for further extraction procedure because it offers better phase separation.

Nature of extracted species :

The composition of complex was confirmed by using log *D* – log *C* plot. The graph log *D*_[Ru^{III}] versus log *C*_[BIMTT] at fixed pH (4.5) was found to be linear and having slope of 1.3 (Fig. 4). Hence the probable composition of extracted species in chloroform has been found to be 1 : 1, [Ru^{III} : BIMTT].

Fig. 4. log *D*_[Ru^{III}] versus log *C*_[BIMTT] curve for determination of composition of complex.

Effect of diverse ions :

Various ions were used in order to assess the tolerance of these ions on the extraction of ruthenium(III) with BIMTT at pH 5.4 acetate buffer solution. Under the optimum condition of the procedure in 25 ml aqueous volume, chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrate, acetate, phosphate, ascorbic acid, EDTA 'disodium salt' (100 mg each); tartarate, citrate, fluoride (50 mg each) did not affect the determination. Among the cations, Co^{II}, Ca^{II}, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III}, Ba^{II}, Sr^{II}, Mg^{II}, Mn^{II} (10 mg each); Al^{III} (7 mg); Ce^{III}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pb^{II}, Hg^{II}, Sn^{II} (5 mg each); Pd^{II}, Au^{III}, Rh^{III}, Pt^{IV}, Pt^{II} (1 mg each), the interferences of Cu^{II} and Mo^{VI} were eliminated by masking with EDTA.

The wide applicability of the method is tested by the analysis of the several synthetic mixtures and Fissium alloys. The proposed spectrophotometric method is simple, rapid, sensitive and is free from the interference of a large number of metal ions including platinum group

Note

metals. To ascertain the selectivity of the reagent, the proposed method was successfully used in the determination of ruthenium(III) in Fission alloys. The sample dissolution is carried out by following literature method¹⁵. The proposed method permits the determination of ruthenium(III) in synthetic mixture containing uranium(VI), zirconium(IV), rhodium(III), palladium(II) and molybdenum(VI). The results of the analysis are reported in Table 1.

100 ml with distilled water and further standardized by gravimetric method¹⁷. A working solution 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ was prepared from it by diluting the stock solution with distilled water. BIMTT (0.01 M) solution was prepared in chloroform. Buffer solution of pH 5.4 was prepared by mixing 88 ml of 0.2 M acetic acid, 412 ml of 0.2 M sodium acetate and diluted to 1000 ml with double distilled water.

Table 1. Spectrophotometric extraction and determination of ruthenium in synthetic mixture corresponding to Fission alloy

Metal ion added (μg)						Ruthenium found ^a	R.S.D.
Ru	Mo	Rh	Pd	Zr	U	(μg)	
200	-	-	-	-	10000	199.6	0.20
200	-	-	-	200	-	199.2	0.21
200	-	-	500	-	-	199.5	0.19
200	-	200	-	-	-	199.4	0.24
200	500	-	-	-	-	199.3	0.23
40	50	1	1	1	1900	39.6	0.20
80	100	2	2	2	3800	79.8	0.22
120	150	3	3	3	5700	119.6	0.24
200	4	4	4	4	7600	199.5	0.25
250	5	5	5	5	9500	249.7	0.21

^aAverage of six determinations.

Experimental

Synthesis of [4-(benzylideneimino)-5-methyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (BIMTT)] :

The 0.02 mole of 3-methyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole¹⁶ and 0.02 mole of benzaldehyde in 50 ml alcohol containing 3 drops of glacial acetic acid were refluxed for 3-4 h. The product obtained was separated and recrystallized from hot ethanol. Light yellow colored needles were obtained (m.p. 140 °C); IR (cm^{-1}) selected band : 763.8 ($\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$), 1691.5 ($\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$), 2941 ($\nu\text{C}-\text{H}$); ¹H NMR (CDCl_3 , TMS; MHz) : 2.12 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 7.3-7.6 (5H, m, aromatic protons), 8.4 (1H, s, $-\text{CH}$), 3.08 (1H, s, $-\text{SH}$).

Equipments and reagents :

Absorbance measurements were made using a Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer (UV-1601) with 1 cm quartz cells was used for measurement. The pH measurements were carried out with an Elico digital pH meter model LI-120 (± 0.01).

A standard stock solution of ruthenium(III) was prepared by dissolving 1 g of ruthenium(III) chloride hydrate in dilute AnalaR hydrochloric acid (1 M) and diluting to

Other standard solutions of different metal ions used to study the effect of foreign ions were prepared by dissolving weighed quantities of respective salts in distilled water or dilute hydrochloric acid. The solutions of anions were prepared by dissolving the respective alkali metal salts in distilled water. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double distilled de-ionised water was invariably used throughout the measurements.

Extraction procedure :

An aqueous solution containing 100 μg of ruthenium(III) was diluted with acetate buffer (pH 5.4) solution up to the mark in 25 ml calibrated flask. The solution was transferred into 125 ml separating funnel. The contents were then equilibrated with 10 ml of 0.01 M BIMTT once for 1 min and the layers were allowed to separate. The light yellow colored organic phase were transferred into 10 ml flask and the volume was made upto the mark with chloroform. The absorbance of the light colored extract was measured at 394 nm against a similarly treated reagent blank. The amount of ruthenium(III) was determined from the calibration curve prepared under optimum condition of the procedure.

Conclusion :

The results underline the potential of the proposed method for the extraction and determination μg level concentration of ruthenium(III) with BIMTT containing low concentration of ruthenium. It is free from the interference of a large number of diverse ions like Co^{II} , Ca^{II} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Ba^{II} , Sr^{II} , Mg^{II} , Mn^{II} etc. which are associated with ruthenium(III) in its natural occurrence. The important features of this method are that low reagent concentration is required, and the time required for the equilibrium is very short (1 min). The method is effective to extract and determine the ruthenium content from the Fissium alloy with regards to sensitivity and selectivity.

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